

AI/ML-driven Predictive Modeling of Drug-Induced Liver Injury (DILI) Severity in Small Molecules

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Abstract

Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) is a complex and multifactorial toxicity that has been a major cause of attrition in drug discovery, development, and post-marketing. Early identification of DILI risk is crucial for reducing the costs and time associated with drug development. While various predictive models based on physicochemical properties or in vitro and in vivo assays have been reported in recent years, these approaches often fail to account for the involvement of liver-expressed proteins in DILI. To bridge this gap, we have developed an integrated artificial intelligence/machine learning (AI/ML) model to predict the severity of DILI for small molecules. Our approach combines physicochemical properties with in silico-predicted off-target interactions to improve accuracy. Our dataset comprises 603 diverse compounds from public databases, classified by the FDA as Most DILI (M-DILI), Less DILI (L-DILI), and No DILI (N-DILI). We utilized six machine learning methods, namely k-nearest neighbor (k-NN), support vector machine (SVM), random forest (RF), Naïve Bayes (NB), artificial neural network (ANN), logistic regression (LR), weighted average ensemble learning (WA), and penalized logistic regression (PLR), to create a consensus model for predicting DILI potential. SVM, RF, LR, WA, and PLR demonstrated the best performance in identifying M-DILI and N-DILI compounds, with a receiver operating characteristic area under the curve of 0.88, sensitivity of 0.73, and specificity of 0.9. Through our analysis, we identified approximately 43 off-targets, in addition to essential physicochemical properties (fsp3, log S, basicity, reactive functional groups, and predicted metabolites), as critical factors in distinguishing between M-DILI and N-DILI compounds. Notable key off-targets include PTGS1, PTGS2, SLC22A12, PPAR γ , RXRA, CYP2C9, AKR1C3, MGLL, RET, AR, and ABCC4. Our AI/ML computational approach shows the significance of integrating physicochemical properties with predicted on- and off-target biological interactions, substantially improving DILI predictivity compared to relying on chemical properties alone. This AI/ML model shows promise in identifying potential DILI risks early, enhancing the probability of success in clinic.